

Emergence of Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) and Reasons behind its Failure in Punjab

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Abstract:

AAP entered into political practice with its first electoral test that was in the 2013 Delhi legislative assembly election, from which it emerged as the second-largest party, winning 28 of the 70 seats. Although it is assumed that there was no scope for AAP in Punjab but Aam Aadmi Party emerged as the giant killer in Punjab by wresting four of the thirteen Parliamentary seats leaving the SAD-BJP alliance with six and pushing the Congress tally down to only three seats in the Lok Sabha elections. AAP saw its speculative graph during Punjab Legislative assembly elections 2017 where AAP broke down its legacy that was made during General Elections 2014 or Delhi assembly Legislative elections 2015. There were several reasons of emergence and breakdown of AAP in context of Punjab which are discussed in paper.

Keyword: Aam Aadmi Party, Political Parties, Elections, Punjab Legislative Assembly.

Abbreviations: AAP Aam Aadmi Party, SAD Srimoni Akali Dal, BJP Bhartiya Janta Party, LS Lok Sabha, IAC India Against Corruption

Introduction:

India is a big country millions and millions of voters, who participate in elections, have shown unflinching faith in democracy, which our country adopted as a system of governance, when it achieved independence in 1947.¹ Successive general election to the house of people and to the assemblies held over the period of last six decades, have demonstrated to the entire world, not only the political maturity of Indian people, but also that democracy has taken firm roots. It has flourished in our country through free and fair elections which form the bedrock of democracy. India has been rightly described by our supreme court as an “oasis of democracy.”

Since the emergence of BJP as a major political party in early 1990s, parliamentary elections at the all india level have mostly been a duel between Congress and BJP, two major parties of Indian ruling classes. Alliance led by these two parties has taken turn to form governments at centre for last two decades. At State level in Punjab, the power had rotated between Congress and Shiromani Akali Dal and its allies. At centre a significant section is projecting BJP or Narendra Modi has promised 'development' and 'good governance'. But the bitter experience of NDA government and BJP ruled states make such promises hardly convincing. More or more people are looking beyond the farcical parliamentary democracy in search of genuine democracy and freedom. This is a political junction where Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) presents itself as an alternative to both Congress and BJP, or at State level in Punjab to both Congress or Shiromani Akali Dal and its allies. It promises change that will clean the corrupt system. It promises to control price rise, solve the basic problem of each or every section of the society and to give political power back to the people usurped from them by country's ruling elite.

Emergence of AAP:

Aam Aadmi Party is an Indian political party, formally launched on 26 November 2012.² It came into existence following differences between the activists Arvind Kejriwal and Anna Hazare regarding whether or not to politicize the popular India Against Corruption (IAC) movement that had been demanding a Jan Lokpal Bill since 2011. Anna Hazare preferred that the movement should remain politically unaligned while Arvind Kejriwal felt the failure of the agitation route necessitated a direct political involvement.

On 2 October 2012 Arvind Kejriwal and his associates announced their decision to form a political party on 26 November. The choice of these dates is quite symbolic 2nd October is Gandhi's birth anniversary, while 26 November is the day the Indian constitution was adopted.³ AAP claimed that the "anti-corruption movement" exposed the anti-people position of all the parliamentary parties which cannot be expected "to work for a corruption-free India". The "movement" tried all means for the enactment of Jan Lokpal Bill, it said, including three indefinite hunger strikes in two years without success. So, the founders of AAP decided that "begging will not work" and that "It is time to uproot these parties and change the whole system" ironically, by forming a new parliamentary party and entering the electoral fray against these parties.

The Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) entered the electoral arena with the aim of benefiting from parliamentary democracy. It is trying to catch the attention of the people with revolutionary rhetoric sheltered in ideological eclecticism consisting of Gandhian 'Ahimsa' and 'Swaraj', 'Socialist' politics of Jayaprakash Narain and 'direct participatory democracy' of the NGOs.⁴

AAP and Punjab:

There are two leading movements occurred in Punjab are Naxalite movement and pro Khalistan movement which play important role for the emergence of AAP in Punjab. Punjabis are very militant by nature and the socio-economic and cultural elements allow these movements to arouse in Punjab.⁵ When the Naxalite movement emerged toiling class become a part of it. After the downfall of Naxalite movement, people shifted into Khalistani Movement. But After these two movements there was a big political gap for alternative politics. In General elections 2014 they feel AAP as an alternative to both existing political parties, SAD and Congress. It is the result of annoyed people which make it possible for four seats for AAP. A party which only a few months ago was essentially unknown on the national political scene, short on funding, and with virtually no organizational infrastructure, managed to secure 25% of the popular vote and four of thirteen Lok Sabha seats in Punjab.⁶

Causes of Defeat of AAP:

When we look at the defeat of Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) and SAD-BJP, it does not surprise us to know that Congress has won 77 seats out of 117 in Punjab Assembly elections 2017. Before we analyses the reasons behind this, let us evaluate the performance of all the three parties. Out of 117 legislative constituencies of Punjab, Congress won 77 seats, SAD-BJP 18 (15+3), and AAP+ Lok Insaf Party 22 (20+2), that is, 38.5%, 28.11%, and 23.7% vote share respectively.⁷ It is interesting to note that in Malwa region of the state, AAP bagged 20 seats while BJP received 1 and SAD 8, out of a total of 69 constituencies in the area. However, in Majha region, Congress won 22 out of 25 whereas SAD and BJP won one each; here, AAP could not even bag one seat. Similarly, in Doaba, Congress, AAP, SAD, and BJP won 15, 2, 5, and 1 respectively.

A party that used to claim its victory, AAP could outnumber SAD-BJP by only four seats while it lagged behind by 4.41% in vote percentage. However, in 2012 legislative assembly

elections, SAD-BJP's vote percentage was 42.05 but this time it has dropped by 13.94%. Similarly, Congress's vote percentage has reduced by 1.61% from 2012 results. AAP being a new party was able to win 4 seats out of 13 in general elections 2014 and that is why it was expected of AAP to succeed in 2017 elections as well. This expectation was alive until the official declaration of Congress' victory.

Now, discussing the scenario constituency wise, Bhagwant Mann, the claimant of CM's position from AAP lost the Jalalabad constituency by 18500 votes from the victorious candidate of SAD, Sukhbir Badal. On the other hand, SAD was able to maintain its victory in three important constituencies, Jalalabad, Lambi, and Majitha. Nevertheless, SAD's other senior leaders had to face defeat, namely, Tota Singh, Adesh Pratap Singh Kairon, and Surjit Singh Rakhra, and simultaneously, Congress' senior leader, namely, Rajinder Kaur Bathal, Sunil Jhakar, Keval Singh Dhillon, and Jagmohan Singh Kang lost the elections. In case of AAP, Gurpreet Ghuggi and Bhagwant Mann joined this list. Further, Sucha Singh Chotepur of Apna Punjab Party (who had separated himself from AAP) lost poorly by winning only 1740 votes.

Therefore, the actual question is that given AAP's tremendous performance in 2014 elections, how it could win only 20 seats in 2017 elections. Despite the propaganda in its favour on social media and beyond, the party had to face major losses in Punjab this time. Let us try to understand the reasons behind this.

1. Inability to Comprehend the Essence of Punjabi Culture:

Punjabi culture and nature has always been a progressive and militant one. The reasons why Naxalite and Khalistani movements could grow and sustain themselves in Punjab were that both of them synchronized with Punjabi culture as well as the nature of its subjects. Despite being a plain area, Guerrilla war could flourish in the state in the time of Mughal reign wherein Punjabis used to loot Mughals and help rescue Indian women from the clutches of Mughals. Secondly, Punjabis have inculcated and accepted other cultures and their values and lifestyles, which demonstrates the progressive value system of Punjab. This is the reason why in absence of Naxalite and Khalistani movements, AAP could win 4 seats in 2014 only in Punjab whereas in all other states, it could not win a single seat. Surprisingly, all these four seats came from the area that was known as the centre of Naxalite. This is to say that AAP

was able to attain significant victory in Punjab because it appealed to revolutionary emotions as well as the history of Punjab. Its comparatively clean image, its agenda of de-corrupting the nation, and many other promises influenced Punjabis, but the same agendas failed to do so in 2017.

This happened because of numerous reasons and the most important of them all is that AAP could not understand the sentiments of Sikhs, who form the majority of the state's populace. AAP's election manifesto had placed the picture of Golden Temple parallel to the broom, AAP's election symbol, from where began the downfall of pro-AAP emotion in Punjab. Secondly, Bhagwant Mann's image was ruined massively as an alcoholic, who was a candidate for the CM's position. Further, Sucha Singh Chotepur organized a press conference and alleged Arvind Kejriwal to be anti-Sikh, and other parties raised the issue of AAP's nominating a non-Punjabi CM since even until the end of the election results, AAP had not announced its official candidate and there were rumors and perceptions that it could be Kejriwal.

2. Perceiving SAD as the Sole Opposition:

Belittling the importance and status of Congress and focusing instead only on SAD as the opposition also led to AAP's defeat. Its main campaign was against SAD on both social media and ground. Its inability to analyse Congress' potential as well as Congress' vote bank affected AAP adversely. Further, the attitude of AAP's politicians, that is, mocking SAD through repeated use of comedy created their own image as 'comedians' and 'non-serious politicians.' Had AAP understood this perception in people's minds, it would have emphasized equally on Congress' politics and mistakes during its propaganda. On the other hand, Congress was smart enough to target SAD and AAP specifically and categorically, which is why Congress won ultimately.

3. The Debate over Punjab's Water Rights:

It is well known that in order to save Punjab's water resources, Punjabis have sacrificed their lives. Despite it, Indian government has consistently discriminated against Punjab by neglecting riparian laws completely. While SAD and Congress could be seen standing in favour of Punjab's waters, AAP's Kejriwal gave a statement on dividing the waters. Further,

his statement only heightened the emotions of people who have always felt discriminated against by Indian state and his being a non-Punjabi worsened the matter. Neither Kejriwal could understand the riparian laws nor the importance of waters for Punjabis.

In 1976, when Indira Gandhi took a prejudiced decision of giving 35 lac acres foot to Punjab and Haryana each, and 80 lac acres foot to Rajasthan, Prakash Singh Badal opposed it vehemently and equated it with a death sentence for farmers of the state. However, Giani Zail Singh did not utter a word, fearing Indira Gandhi, and the then Punjab government accepted two crores from Haryana government to make Satluj Yamuna Link. Afterwards, as soon as Prakash Singh Badal became the next CM, he accepted the remaining payment for SYL.

On the other hand, Haryana's CM, Devilal tried to convince Badal and the then PM, Moraji Desai to divide the waters of Punjab. Moraji organized a meeting with both the CMs, analysed the path of the rivers of Punjab, and announced that Haryana has no right whatsoever over any of the river of Punjab. When Devilal argued that Punjab had already been giving its waters to Haryana, Moraji replied that Punjabis were foolish enough to let that happen. However, now, Punjabis have come to realize and feel the suppression on them and their waters because of SYL. Hence, it is evident why Kejriwal's comment on the division of waters was met with so much resistance in the state.

4. Displacement of Politicians with Untainted Reputation:

After expelling Prashant Bhushan and Yogendra Yadav, AAP expelled Dharamveer Gandhi in Punjab. Moreover, Sucha Singh Chotepur was shown the way out because of the disputable sting operation on him. Nevertheless, AAP paid the price of it by losing good leadership in Punjab.

5. Uncertainty Due to the Absence of a CM Candidate:

It is probably the first time a party contested elections without an official face for the post of CM in Punjab. Congress and SAD had already announced their CMs, and had thus appealed to the personality cult politics of the state. AAP, however, remained oblivious of the fact and thus, faced a shameful defeat.

Conclusion:

It is clear from the above stated arguments that AAP lost because of its inability to understand Punjab's politics as well as the expectations of Punjabis from their CM. However, another noteworthy factor has been the role played by the politics of creating 'strong' personalities in the last two elections. Be it Trump, Modi, or Captain, people have chosen candidates that have appealed to their sensibilities of giving power to a 'strong' and 'articulate' individual.

References

1. Verma P.S, Punjab Assembly Elections, New Delhi: Economic and political Weekly, 15 July 2002, p. 2281.
2. <https://aamaadmiparty.org/about/our-history/> Accessed: May 5, 2019.
3. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-20492056> Accessed: May 5, 2019.
4. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/aam-aadmi-party-is-socialist-not-silly-says-its-policy-guru-yogendra-yadav/articleshow/27868551.cms?from=mdr> Accessed: May 7, 2019.
5. Singh, Pritam, Aam Aadmi Party as Third Player in Punjab Politics, Economic and political Weekly, Vol. 52, Issue No. 3, 21 Jan, 2017.
6. Sekhon Jagrup Singh, The Real Star in Punjab is AAP The Hindu May 25, 2014. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/the-real-star-in-punjab-is-aap/article6045240.ece> Accessed: May 8, 2019.
7. Election Commission of India- State Election, 2017 to the Legislative Assembly of Punjab. <https://eci.gov.in/files/file/3614-punjab-general-legislative-election-2017/> Accessed: May 10, 2019.